

WHY COPENHAGEN?

WHY THE 1927 COPENHAGEN INTERPRETATION OF QUANTUM PHYSICS?

**Why did we physicists of Earth work together to create
the 1927 Copenhagen Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics?**

by

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September 20, 2023

Keywords: Why Copenhagen? Why the 1927 Copenhagen Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics? Werner Heisenberg, Max Born, Niels Bohr, Wolfgang Pauli, Albert Einstein, Erwin Schrodinger, Newton's 1687 Force Laws, Young's 1801 Double-Slit Experiment, The 1865 Maxwell Equations, The 1888 Rydberg Formula, The 1895 Lorentz Force, The 1913 Bohr Atom, The 1922 Stern-Gerlach Experiment, The 1935 Elements of Physical Reality (EPR), Schrodinger's Cat of 1935, The EPR Quantum Entanglement 1935 Thought Experiment, The 1935 Einstein-Rosen Bridge (ER Bridge), The 1950 Incompleteness of the Description, The 1951 de Broglie-Bohm Reawakening, The 1964 Bell's Theorem, The 1972 Clauser Experiment, The 1982 Aspect Experiment, The Zeilinger Experiments, A 1993 Wave Action Conservation Realization, The Initial 2013 ER=EPR Quantum Postulate, The Deeper 2016 ER Wormholes = EPR Entanglement Realization, Our Current Views of Quantum Mechanics are Provisional in 2016, A Helpful 2022 Quantum Realization, Our Current Quantum Situation Today in 2023.

ABSTRACT

Why Copenhagen? Why did we physicists of Earth *choose* to create the Copenhagen Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics during the *wild days* of the 1920's? And why did most of us scientists continue to believe in it for nearly a whole century afterwards? Why would we actually do such a thing to ourselves? Did we have any other alternatives? Do any of the other interpretations of quantum physics make any more sense? Why would anyone want to discover a "*correct*" interpretation? Why do some of us still seek for a "*complete*" interpretation? Is quantum physics a real physical thing, that can be physically studied, in a real physical laboratory? Or is quantum physics just a mathematical statistical probabilistic thing, that can only be contemplated intellectually inside our human brains? This brief article attempts to ask some of these important questions, in the hope that it might further encourage others to continue to ask their wise scientific questions, and even to start asking much *better* questions, until that bright joyful day finally arrives, when we scientists of Earth, can *all* wisely agree together on the very *best* answers.

INTRODUCTION

Was physics *easier* to *understand* centuries ago?

Perhaps yes.

For example, the 1687 force laws of Sir Isaac Newton [1], the 1801 double-slit experiment of Thomas Young [2], the 1865 Maxwell's Equations of electromagnetism [3], the 1888 Rydberg formula for the spectrum of the hydrogen atom [4], the 1895 electromagnetic Lorentz force [5], and the 1913 Bohr atom [6], *all* seemed *understandable*, at least to some of us initially.

Why didn't we simply stick with these seemingly *understandable theories*?

Why exactly did we physicists choose to invent (or support) our "*Copenhagen Interpretation*" of Quantum Physics, with its strange ideas, that still seem difficult to understand?

And *when* precisely, did we physicists of Earth, actually proceed to invent our strange Copenhagen Interpretation?

Did some of us *rush* too quickly to our bold new scientific conclusions in the 1920's?

Did we look really *deeply*, and very carefully, at *all* our available logical options then?

“SPACE QUANTIZATION”

Some early parts of the *wild* Copenhagen Interpretation of Quantum Physics may have already been intellectually invented prior to 1927.

For example, when Otto Stern and Walther Gerlach initially published [7] the experimental results of their famous Stern-Gerlach magnetic experiment in 1922, they choose a presumptuous title to boldly proclaim to the whole wide world, that they themselves had indeed finally observed “*Space Quantization*”.

This early type of wild “*Copenhagen Interpretation*” may have received a forceful *social boost* about 5 years later, when Max Born and Werner Heisenberg jointly delivered their *charismatic* closed-theory speech [8] during October 24-29, 1927 at the 5th Solvay Conference in Brussels, Belgium.

What exactly did Heisenberg and Born say during their influential matrix-math *closed-theory* presentation?

A CLOSED THEORY

In their famous *closed-theory* speech, these two well-respected physicists together boldly proclaimed that:

“... we consider *quantum mechanics*
to be ***a closed theory***,
whose fundamental physical
and mathematical assumptions
are no longer susceptible
of *any* modification.”

Exactly how were their two human brains influenced, to such a degree, so as to actually cause them both to boldly make such a *closed-theory claim*, in front of so many of their own academic scientific peers?

Has *any* one of us physicists of Earth, be able to learn *any* more about quantum mechanics, since their *closed-theory speech* in October 1927?

Did both Niels Bohr and Wolfgang Pauli *fully* support this overbearing October 1927 closed-theory speech?

4 BRAIN THEORY

Did the combined intellectual strength, of these *4 Powerful Influential Brains*, somehow win over the hearts and minds of most of the other Solvay Conference participants?

Were there any brave *dissenters* at Solvay in 1927?

What was the full academic *cost of dissent* against the current majority viewpoint (mainstream science) in 1927 and 1928?

Why did Louis de Broglie *abandon* his promising “Pilot Wave Theory” in 1928?

Why did Albert Einstein publish his *dissenting* EPR quantum entanglement paper in 1935? [9]

Why did Erwin Schrödinger publish his *dissenting* Schrödinger’s Cat paper in 1935? [10]

Why was Albert Einstein *never* able to feel comfortable with the prevailing *orthodox* Copenhagen Interpretation of Quantum Physics?

What about it was *really* bothering him?

What really worried Einstein about Copenhagen?

1950 EINSTEIN to SCHRODINGER

In a December 22, 1950 letter [11] that Albert Einstein wrote to Erwin Schrödinger, he wrote about his *strong desire* to discover a *more-complete theory* of quantum physics.

In this revealing *letter* to his dear friend Erwin Schrödinger, Einstein mentioned Schrödinger's 1935 Cat; and he also referred to the 1926 complex-valued Ψ -*function* (Schrodinger's Wave Function) as only representing an *incomplete* description of *physical reality*.

In this revealing letter, Albert Einstein forcefully expressed his personal, longstanding, scientific conviction regarding the *incompleteness*, of the 1926 Schrödinger Wave Function's *description of reality*.

Here is an English translation of what Albert Einstein wrote to his dear friend Erwin Schrödinger on December 22, 1950:

22 XII 1950

Dear Schrödinger,

You are the only contemporary physicist, besides Laue, who sees that one cannot get around *the assumption of reality* — if only one is *honest*.

Most of them simply do not see what sort of risky game they are playing with *reality* — reality as something independent of what is experimentally established.

They somehow believe that the quantum theory provides a *description of reality*, and even a *complete description*; this interpretation is, however, refuted, most elegantly by your system of radioactive atom + Geiger counter + amplifier + charge of gun powder + cat in a box, in which the ψ -function of the system contains the cat both alive and blown to bits.

Is the state of the cat to be created only when a physicist investigates the situation at some definite time?

Nobody really doubts that the presence or absence of the cat is something independent of the act of observation.

But then the description by means of the ψ -function is *certainly incomplete*, and there must be *a more complete description*.

If one wants to consider the quantum theory as final (in principle), then one must believe that *a more complete description* would be useless because there would be no laws for it.

If that were so, then physics could only claim the interest of shopkeepers and engineers; the whole thing would be a *wretched bungle*.

You are completely right to emphasize that the *complete description* cannot be built on the concept of acceleration, nor, it seems to me, can it be built on the particle concept.

Only one of the tools of our trade remains — the *field* concept, but God knows whether this will *stand firm*.

I think it is worthwhile to hold on to this, i.e., the continuum, as long as one has no really sound arguments against it.

But it seems certain to me that the fundamentally *statistical* character of the theory, is simply a *consequence* of the *incompleteness* of the *description*.

This says nothing about the *deterministic* character of the theory; that is a thoroughly nebulous concept anyway, so long as one does not know how much has to be given in order to *determine* the *initial state* (“cut”).

It is rather rough to see that we are still in the stage of our swaddling clothes, and it is not surprising that the fellows struggle *against* admitting it (even to themselves).

Best regards!

Yours,

A. Einstein

In his first paragraph Einstein wrote about scientific *honesty* and the assumption of *reality*.

Did Albert Einstein really believe there were *only 3* honest physicists on planet Earth in December 1950?

Did Albert Einstein believe that the Copenhagen Interpretation might have some *dishonest* components?

Did Albert Einstein also believe that the Copenhagen Interpretation might have some *missing* components?

Evidently, Albert Einstein didn't have too much confidence in most of the dozens of physicists he personally knew in 1950.

1951 EINSTEIN calls BOHM

One bright, young, *open-minded* physicist that Einstein took a particular liking to was named David Bohm.

Albert Einstein made an impactful *phone call* to David Bohm in 1951, and then David Bohm promptly proceeded to rediscover the 1920's "*Pilot Wave Theory*" of Louis de Broglie. [12]

Did Albert Einstein possibly mention to David Bohm *anything* about de Broglie's Pilot Wave Theory of the 1920's?

Or, did David Bohm completely rediscover de Broglie's Pilot Wave Theory, all by himself alone, without any real hints or *prompting* from Einstein?

PILOT WAVE THEORY

This unorthodox Pilot Wave Theory was a *dissenting idea* from the orthodox Copenhagen Interpretation of Quantum Physics.

Evidently, some of these *dissenting ideas* of de Broglie, Bohm, and Einstein, found their way into the bright, young, receptive brain of John Stewart Bell, who was then inspired to publish his illuminating Bell's Theorem ideas in 1964. [13]

1964 BELL'S THEOREM

These helpful Bell's Theorem concepts of 1964, were tested in 1972 by John Clauser [14], and then tested again in 1982 by Alain Aspect [15], and then tested again and again by Anton Zeilinger [16]; which resulted in these *three courageous* experimental *physicists* jointly receiving the Nobel Prize in Physics in October 2022. [17]

So where do we stand today in 2023?

Does the Copenhagen Interpretation of Quantum Physics *still* reign supremely unchallenged in the minds and hearts of most of today's physicists?

INDEPENDENT-MINDED PHYSICISTS

Or are some of us *independent-minded physicists* (like Einstein, Schrödinger, de Broglie, and Bohm) already starting to *question* the old orthodox Copenhagen Interpretation, even today in 2023?

For example, just a couple decades ago, in 1997, Max Tegmark published [18] an interesting paper, in which he showed that some bright physicists are *already* starting to turn their mortal minds away from the Copenhagen Interpretation, in favor of other interpretations, like the Many Worlds Interpretation [19] of Hugh Everett, and the de Broglie Bohm Interpretation [20] of David Bohm and Louis de Broglie.

For another example, when we published a paper in 1993 [21] about a very general form of Wave Action Conservation, we also realized that Wave Action (*Angular Momentum*) was probably conserved for all physical systems of this entire universe, including *all quantum* systems, of *any size*; and that this powerful wave action conservation *law*, might be used someday to form a proper deterministic basis, for a more-complete physical explanation, of why electrons, protons, and neutrons all *always maintain* an intrinsic *angular momentum* of exactly half of Planck's Constant; and the Copenhagen Interpretation will *not be needed* for this intrinsic determination.

2013 ER = EPR

For another example, just one decade ago, in a brilliant paper published in 2013 [22], Juan Maldacena and Leonard Susskind basically suggested that their interesting idea of “*ER=EPR*” could perhaps give us all a *fresh new way* forward towards building a better quantum theory.

Then just 3 years later in 2016, Leonard Susskind bravely published *Copenhagen vs Everett, Teleportation, and ER=EPR* [23].

EXPERT QUANTUM OPINIONS

In this very-insightful 2016 paper, Leonard Susskind discusses how, until just recently, his own *scientific opinions* of quantum mechanics had mostly coincided with those other weighty scientific opinions, of other world-renowned physicists, such as Richard Feynman and Paul Dirac, namely:

“Quantum mechanics

is so confusing

that I can't even tell if there is a problem,

but maybe it's all ok because it works.

*There is probably not much profit in thinking about ‘interpretations’
and even less in arguing about them.”*

Leonard Susskind then further elaborates on how his personal scientific views have recently changed:

*But over the last two years
I’ve come to **see it differently**.*

*Now I feel that our **current views**
of quantum mechanics are **provisional**;
it’s the best we can do
without a much **deeper** understanding
of its connection with **gravity**,
but it’s **not final**.*

*The reason involves a very particular development,
the so-called **ER=EPR** principle.*

*ER=EPR tells us that the immensely complicated network
of **entangled subsystems**
that comprises the universe
is also an immensely complicated*

(and technically complex)
network of Einstein-Rosen bridges.

*To me it seems obvious that if ER=EPR is true
it is a very big deal,
and it must affect the foundations
and **interpretation** of quantum mechanics.*

A PROVISIONAL THEORY

Is Leonard Susskind almost suggesting that our beloved 96-year-old Copenhagen Interpretation can be safely viewed as being merely a temporary “*provisional theory*” until we physicists of Earth can discover a better interpretation?

For another, more-recent example, just a few months ago on December 26, 2022, Aurélien Drezet published [24] a very interesting paper in which he wrote:

“Seventy years ago, the main-stream and leading journal *Physical Review* published two articles by David Bohm with the titles ‘*A suggested interpretation of the quantum theory in terms of hidden variables (parts I and II)*’ [20] submitted together the 5th of July 1951 and published the 15th of January 1952 in the same volume.

It is true to say that these two articles had, on the long term, a *tremendous effect* on the scientific community.

Without this work by Bohm, John Bell would *probably not* have even considered the ***nonlocality issue*** as a serious problem, and as a consequence, he would not have

discovered his famous theorem ‘*On the Einstein Podolsky Rosen Paradox*’ [13].

Subsequently, if after Bohm, Bell would not have written his cornerstone articles, we can speculate that *neither* John Clauser, Alain Aspect, *nor* Anton Zeilinger would have started their experimental projects; and therefore, would *not* have won the Nobel prize this year ‘*for experiments with entangled photons, establishing the violation of Bell inequalities and pioneering quantum information science*’.

Nevertheless, and despite all the scientific achievements and technological implications based on quantum entanglement, it is also fair to say that if everything started with some fundamental questions concerning reality and hidden variables, the work of Bohm was *badly received* in the 1950’s at a time when even asking if hidden variables could exist, and explain the underlying quantum reality, was considered as an *anathema*.

For the community, David Joseph Bohm became immediately one of those *heretics*, like Einstein or Schrödinger, criticizing the *orthodox* Copenhagen quantum interpretation.”

It seems like Einstein’s wise spoken words may have influenced the receptive mind of David Bohm in 1951.

It also seems like Bohm’s wise written words may have influenced the receptive mind of John Stewart Bell in 1952.

It also seems like Bell’s wise published words of 1964 may have influenced the receptive minds of John Clauser, Alain Aspect, and Anton Zeilinger.

It also seems possible that the most recent October 4th, 2022 Nobel Prize in Physics, shared by Zeilinger, Aspect, and Clauser, may one day *inspire* a whole new generation of bright young physicists, to start looking more deeply at the ***nonlocality issue*** that is patiently abiding its own time inside the very physical heart of *quantum entanglement*.

A LIBERATING IDEA

Perhaps, the really liberating idea, that Aurélien Drezet presented on December 26, 2022, is that the set of early *dissenting viewpoints*, of Einstein, Schrödinger, de Broglie, and Bohm, may have actually *encouraged* and *inspired* Bell, Clauser, Aspect, and Zeilinger to each proceed forward with their own proper scientific confidence, to bravely do what they each subsequently did for this world.

INSPIRING DISSENT

Can a *dissenting* viewpoint *inspire* good scientific work?

Could it be possible that some *dissenting minority viewpoints* can sometimes actually be good for science, if these dissenting minority viewpoints can somehow *inspire* us all (or at least some of us) to search diligently for something *better* than the existing, dominant, mainstream, prevailing orthodox scientific views of our own times?

How about even today in 2023?

GOODBYE COPENHAGEN?

Is it now time for us all to find our own personal courage to start saying *goodbye* to our old orthodox Copenhagen Interpretation of this past century?

Or will it always *feel* much *safer* for us, to continue to hold fast and firm in our own scientific minds and intellectual hearts, to our beloved, old, tried-and-true Copenhagen Interpretation of Quantum Physics?

If most of us physicists do *eventually* choose to let go of our beloved old Copenhagen Interpretation, then with *what exactly* will we elect to replace it?

And how will we know for sure if we have chosen *wisely*?

Can we discover any new *experimental* tests that can help us all to choose wisely as the bright physicists of Earth?

CONCLUSION

Why Copenhagen? Why exactly did we create the Copenhagen Interpretation in the first place, about a century ago?

Was our 1927 Copenhagen Interpretation the intellectual product of careful *logical* thinking, and diligent experimentation in the scientific laboratory?

Or was our 1927 Copenhagen Interpretation the intellectual product of powerful mortal egos, and *unbridled* academic pride?

Or was our 1927 Copenhagen Interpretation the intellectual product of some combination of *both*?

Why did we create Copenhagen really?

Now that we the people of Earth have *already* managed to *live* with the Copenhagen Interpretation of Quantum Physics for 96 years, from 1927 to 2023, what shall we do with it today?

Shall we abandon it?

Or shall we keep it?

What shall we do with it *today* for the intellectual benefit of *all* humankind here on Earth?

Can any of us wise ones (*homo sapiens*) think of an actual *physical experiment* that we can scientifically conduct in our laboratories with today's technologies, to help us to *intelligently decide* what to do with our 96-year-old Copenhagen Interpretation of Quantum Physics?

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